

CULTURAL BARRIERS IN TRANSLATING ANIMAL IDIOMS FROM ENGLISH TO RUSSIAN

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This article shows us the role of idiomatic expressions based on animals, focusing on English and Russian languages. It discusses idioms as phraseological units with structural integrity and cultural significance, which based on the history and traditions of their speakers. The study compares animal-related idioms in both languages, displaying the challenges of literal translation and the importance of it's usage. Using examples from literature and everyday speech, the article shows how idioms enrich language and how they often summarize into single words in English. It concludes by emphasizing the importance of mastering idioms through immersion and interaction with native speakers for effective language learning and cultural understanding.

Idioms are some of the most culturally specific parts of language because their meanings are not clear from a literal reading. Phraseological units show national mindset, historical context, and cultural traditions. Animal idioms are particularly significant since people often describe human behavior by comparing it to animals. These expressions come from folklore, mythology, and everyday life. Language serves as a way to communicate, reflecting culture, worldview, and social experience. One of the most expressive features of language is idiomatic expression. Idioms consist of fixed combinations of words, and their meanings are not clear from literal interpretation. They convey figurative meanings that are specific to a culture and carry emotional weight.

Idioms play an important role in everyday communication as well as in literary discourse because they enrich speech, make expression more vivid, and reflect national ways of thinking. Due to their figurative nature, idioms often present serious difficulties for translators. The meaning of an idiom is usually connected with cultural associations shared by speakers of a particular language community. As a result, direct translation rarely preserves the original meaning or stylistic effect.

Translation scholars emphasize that idioms are closely connected with culture and therefore require intercultural competence rather than word-for-word translation¹. The symbolic meaning of animals differs across cultures, which creates serious difficulties when translating idioms from English into Russian. The aim of this research is to analyze cultural barriers in translating animal idioms and to determine effective translation strategies.

Idioms contribute significantly to expressiveness and stylistic richness of speech. They allow speakers to communicate complex meanings concisely while simultaneously conveying emotional colouring, evaluation, or irony. Through figurative language, idioms make communication more vivid and natural, particularly in everyday conversation, literature,

¹ Baker M. In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation. — 70 ctp.

journalism, and media discourse. Their frequent use demonstrates how language reflects cultural perception of reality. Although many languages employ figurative expressions, the images and metaphors used are shaped by cultural traditions and shared social experience. As a result, idioms often contain implicit cultural references that may not be immediately understandable to speakers of other languages. This cultural dependence explains why idioms present significant challenges in translation and intercultural communication. According to V.V. Vinogradov, phraseology reflects collective cultural consciousness and forms an important part of national linguistic identity². Animal imagery functions as a universal metaphorical system; however, its interpretation depends on cultural traditions. For example:

as sly as a fox — *хитрый как лиса*

a dark horse — *тёмная лошадка*

eat like a horse — *есть как лошадь*

Some idioms have direct equivalents, while others require adaptation due to cultural differences. Peter Newmark argues that translation equivalence depends primarily on cultural compatibility rather than lexical similarity³.

Animals symbolize different human qualities such as wisdom, courage, or stupidity. Nevertheless, symbolic associations vary between cultures. Researchers distinguish absence of equivalents in the target language⁴.

For instance, the fox symbolizes cunning in both English and Russian cultures, while the owl represents wisdom mainly in English tradition. For Example: *Wise as an owl* – *мудрый как сова*. This expression exists in Russian but the symbolism of wisdom connected with the owl is historically more prominent and productive in English usage.

The main problems in translating animal idioms include lack of equivalents, metaphorical mismatch, and cultural specificity⁵. Literal translation often leads to misunderstanding because idioms express figurative rather than literal meaning. One of the most common difficulties is the lack of direct equivalents in the target language. Some English animal idioms do not have an established Russian idiomatic counterpart. In such cases, translators must replace the idiom with a descriptive phrase or another expression conveying similar meaning. For example: the expression "*When pigs fly*" literally translates as "*когда свиньи полетят*" but the correct equivalent would be "*когда рак на горе свистнет*".

Russian does not use pigs as a symbol of impossibility; therefore, literal translation sounds unnatural. The translator must convey the meaning rather than preserve the image.

Another difficulty involves metaphorical mismatch, where the same idea exists in both languages but is expressed through different animal imagery. Cultural traditions influence which animals symbolize particular qualities. For example: the expression "*As busy as a bee*" – *трудится как пчела*. Here the metaphor coincides and translation is easy.

The linguist Eugene Nida introduced the concept of dynamic equivalence, according to which translation should produce the same communicative effect on the reader⁶. The

² Vinogradov V.V. Russian Phraseology. — Moscow: Vysshaya Shkola, 1986. — 45 стр.

³ Newmark P. A Textbook of Translation. — New York: Prentice Hall, 1988. — 103–105 стр.

⁴ Zhang L., Li S. Translation of English Animal Idioms in Intercultural Communication. — 2020. — 52–54 стр.

⁵ Niyadullayeva S. Translating Idioms Across Cultures. — 2022. — 27–29 стр.

⁶ Nida E., Taber C. The Theory and Practice of Translation. — Leiden: Brill, 2003. — 12–14 стр.

translation of idiomatic expressions requires special strategies because idioms rarely allow direct word-for-word translation. Equivalent idiom substitution is considered the most effective strategy when a target language possesses an idiom with the same figurative meaning and similar stylistic value. In this case, the translator replaces the source idiom with a functionally equivalent expression used naturally by target language speakers. This strategy allows preservation of imagery, emotional colouring, and communicative impact. For example: the English idiom *"don't look a gift horse in the mouth"* corresponds closely to the Russian expression *"дарёному коню в зубы не смотрят"*. Such equivalence ensures that the translated text sounds authentic and culturally appropriate.

Cultural substitution is used when there is no direct idiomatic translation, but a cultural image can be used instead. In this case, the translator will substitute the original metaphorical expression with another image that can be understood in the target culture. The main aim is not to translate the original lexical image but to translate the meaning. This technique shows the role of the translator as an intercultural mediator who changes cultural references to ensure target audience understanding. For Example: *kill two birds with one stone*. Literal translation would be: *убить двух птиц одним камнем*. Cultural substitution: *убить двух зайцев одним выстрелом*.

The English image involves birds, while Russian idiomatic tradition refers to hares. Despite different animals, both idioms convey the idea of achieving two goals with one action.

Descriptive translation, or paraphrasing, is used when there is no equivalent idiomatic expression or cultural substitute. In this situation, the figurative meaning of the idiom is described using a neutral descriptive phrase. This translation technique may lack stylistic expressiveness but ensures semantic clarity and avoids misunderstandings. Descriptive translation is commonly used in academic writing, technical translation, or situations where accuracy is more valuable than stylistic imitation. Mona Baker notes that successful idiom translation preserves communicative function rather than lexical structure¹. For Example: *white elephant* - an expensive but useless possession. Descriptive translation: *дорогая, но бесполезная вещь*.

Literal translation becomes feasible only when the symbolic associations of the idiom are the same in both languages. When cultures have similar metaphorical interpretations, the original image can be translated without losing meaning. However, this strategy must be applied carefully, as literal translation frequently produces unnatural or misleading expressions if cultural equivalence is incomplete⁴.

These strategies demonstrate that idiom translation is primarily an intercultural process. Comparative analysis shows that English idioms frequently originate from hunting traditions and maritime culture, whereas Russian idioms are influenced by folklore and agrarian life. Therefore, translators must interpret cultural meaning rather than translate words mechanically. For example:

hold your horses - *подожди*

let sleeping dogs lie - *не буди лихо, пока оно тихо*

This study contributes to the broader field of translation studies by emphasizing the importance of balancing fidelity to meaning with naturalness and readability in the target

language. Future research could expand this analysis to include idioms from other languages or explore how idiomatic translation is taught in educational settings

The research confirms that cultural barriers constitute the main difficulty in translating animal idioms from English into Russian. Idioms function as carriers of cultural knowledge and national mentality. Successful translation requires linguistic competence combined with cultural awareness. The analysis has shown that phraseological units create significant challenges for translators, mainly because their meanings are not always clear or directly transferable from one language to another. Unlike ordinary word combinations, phraseologisms carry figurative meanings and reflect the cultural background of the people who use them. For this reason, literal translation often fails to convey the intended message. A successful translation therefore requires not only linguistic knowledge but also an understanding of cultural context, stylistic nuances, and the communicative purpose of the expression, mostly with native speakers. Only by considering all these aspects together translators can preserve both the meaning and the expressive value of phraseological units in the target language.

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